

Impact of Magnetically Treated Water on Growth Rate And Haematological Parameters of Dutch And Chinchilla Rabbits

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ABSTRACT

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Rabbit is a source of protein and commercialization of rabbit production in Nigeria is essential to improve food security and meet the demand. Some rabbit farms have problems of poor growth rate, high mortality and high cost of animal feed causing high production cost. Magnetically treated water (MTW) could improve growth performance and boost immunity of animals for profitable rabbit farming. This study was conducted to assess the impact of MTW on growth rate and haematological parameters of rabbits. Twenty rabbits (10 Dutch, 10 Chinchilla species) 4 weeks old with average body-weight of 400g were kept in wooden pen-house (150×100×100cm), 5 rabbits/pen for 15 weeks. MTW was produced by passing water through pipe surrounded with 30 pieces of neodymium magnet (15,000 Gauss). Dutch and Chinchilla rabbits that were given MTW were denoted D₁ and C₁ while Dutch and Chinchilla rabbits that were given non-magnetically treated water (NMTW) were denoted D₂ and C₂. Each pen-house was provided with 1kg of same diet and 2litres of MTW or NMTW daily. Growth rate (body weight) was measured weekly; blood samples were collected and analyzed using standard methods. Mean body weights of the rabbit at 15 weeks for D₁, C₁, D₂, C₂ were 1925.58, 1878.11, 1704.87 and 1592.51 g, respectively. Red blood cells (RBC) counts for D₁, C₁, D₂ and C₂ were $4.48 \times 10^{12}/L$, $3.36 \times 10^{12}/L$, $1.69 \times 10^{12}/L$ and $1.54 \times 10^{12}/L$, respectively. White blood cells (WBC) were $5.6 \times 10^9/L$, $5.1 \times 10^9/L$, $4.4 \times 10^9/L$ and $2.9 \times 10^9/L$. MTW increased the body weight by 12.9-17.93%, improved the immunity with higher RBC, WBC. MTW is recommended for rabbit production.

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INTRODUCTION

Rabbit is a source of quality protein with less cholesterol compared to other animals like chicken, beef and pork. Commercialization of rabbit production in Nigeria is essential to improve food security and meet the high demand in the country. Some rabbit farms in Nigeria are facing problems of poor growth rate, high mortality and high cost of animal feed causing high cost of production. In this 21st century, researchers are looking for methods that are environmentally friendly and economical for improving productivity of agriculture (both plant and animal) for better standard of living especially in developing countries like Nigeria. The earth's magnetic field has positive effect human's health and improves productivity of plant and animal. Therefore, magnetic field could be used to enhance productivity of plant and animal. Magnetized water which is also called magnetically treated water increased crop yield and increased milk production of dairy animals (Othman et al., 2009; Yacout et al., 2015). Al-hummodet al. (2024) reported that magnetized water had positive impact on the growth rate and increased body weight of ducks and rabbit, enhanced feed conversion efficiency of domestic ducks and rabbit. Magnetized water also improved the haematological and biochemical parameters of the blood, enhanced liver function, reduced cholesterol, urea, Aspartate Aminotransferase (AST) and Alanine Aminotransferase (ALT) enzyme activity (Al-hummodet al., 2024). Mahmoud et al. (2015) pointed out that magnetized water improved the productive performance of rabbit, enhanced liver and renal functions of rabbits.

Jiaxun et al. (2020) reported that magnetically treated water as drinking water for rabbit enhanced feed intake, increased the rate of digestion and assimilation, increased growth rate in term of body weight of rabbits. Yacout et al. (2015) also pointed out that magnetically treated water improved water quality which enhances nutrient digestibility and accelerates growth rate of goats. Mahmoud et al. (2015) concluded that drinking magnetically treated water (magnetized water) could be a good promising practice for improving productivity, growth performance, prevents liver diseases, enhanced liver and renal function of rabbits. Ebrahim and Azab (2017) revealed that magnetically treated water improved the qualities of blood parameters, biochemical, semen, and antioxidant status in human and animals. Drinking magnetized water by the domestic animals could prevent and breaking up kidney stone and gall bladder stone Ebrahim and Azab (2017). Mahmoud et al. (2019) reported that magnetically treated water increased red blood cells (RBC), hemoglobin (Hb) and hematocrit (HCT) as compared to rabbits that were given non magnetized water. El-Hanoun et al. (2013) indicated that magnetized water significantly increased the body weight of rabbit within 6 -12 weeks of age when the water was treated with 4000 Gauss. Therefore, magnetized water is a non-chemical method and a simple technology that could be used to boost the productivity of rabbit and other domestic animals. The technology

could be seen as a promising method for boosting agricultural productivity which can increase the availability of food especially in the developing countries like Nigeria.

Production of magnetized water could be done by using permanent magnet or electromagnet to generate magnetic field through which water will flow. The effectiveness of the treatment depends on magnetic field strength, flow rate of water through the magnetic field and the resident time of the water in the magnetic field. In the previous studies, Maheshwari and Grewal (2009) reported that magnetic flux density of 35 - 1360 G measured inside the pipe was effective for producing magnetized water for irrigation. Podlesny et al. (2004) concluded that allowing water to flow through magnetic field for 15 s was adequate and effective for producing magnetized water while Aladjadjiyan (2007) recommended 60 to 600 s for producing magnetized water. This means that magnetic flux density of 35 – 1360 G inside pipe where the water is flowing is adequate for producing magnetized water. Also, the residence time of 15 – 600 s is effective for producing magnetized water. The objectives of this paper were to determine the Impact of magnetically treated water on the growth rate and haematological parameters of rabbit.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Ethics Statement

Ethical approval was obtained from the Department of Agricultural and Biosystems Engineering, University of Ilorin, Nigeria (Approval Date: 23 June 2025).

Pen-House For The Rabbit

The pen-house for the rabbits was constructed using wooden plank. The pen-house was 100 × 100 cm and 700 cm long but it was partitioned into four equal parts with a wooden plank of 100 × 100 cm and each pen-house was 100 × 100 × 150 cm. The top of the pen-house was covered with a wire mesh for ventilation. The pen-house was supported with 2 by 2 inches (12.9 by 12.9 cm) wooden stand and 70 cm in height so that the pen-house is 70 cm above the ground surface. Dutch rabbit and Chinchilla rabbit species were used in this study with five rabbits in each partitioned pen-house (100 × 100 × 150 cm). Each pen-house was supplied with a 3 litres capacity of clay pot that was filled with water from which the rabbits drink water. The pen-house where the rabbits were kept was shown in Figures 1 and 2 for the Dutch and Chinchilla rabbits. The pen-house was put under a shed to prevent rainfall into the pen-house but the rabbits were exposed to light. A total of twenty rabbits (10 Dutch and 10 Chinchilla species) at four weeks old with average body-weight of 400g were used in this study. Five rabbits were put in each pen-house(150×100×100cm) for 15 weeks and 500 g of pellet feed was provided in each pen-house per day. Pellet feed was chosen because

it encourages the rabbit to drink more water than when succulent green-grasses are given.

Figure 1. Dutch rabbit in the pen-house

Figure 2. Chinchilla rabbit in the pen-house

Production of Magnetically Treated Water

The magnetic treatment chamber consists of a square metallic pipe 12×12 mm and 1000 mm long that was cut into two and put in two layers with each length is 500 mm. A total of 30 pieces of neodymium magnet rated 1.5 Tesla (15,000 Gauss) by the manufacturer were used for treating the water. The two square metallic pipes were put in two layers and connected together with 12.7 mm hose, 10 pieces of neodymium magnet were put on the two sides of the pipe and in between the two layers of the pipes. This was done to effectively utilize the few available 30 pieces of neodymium magnets to achieve 1000 mm length of the magnetic treatment chamber instead of 750 mm. The principle also makes the magnetic treatment unit (chamber) more compact and occupies small space. The magnetic field strength in the pipe where the water was flowing was measured using a Gaussmeter (Model GM-2 by Alpha Lab Inc) and recorded as 4000 G (400 mT). The magnetic treatment chamber was connected to a 50 litres storage tank with 25.4 mm pipe and a control tap for regulating the flow of water from the storage tank. The water given to rabbit was obtained from tap water supplied for the public by the Kwara State Water Cooperation, Ilorin. The water was allowed to flow through the magnetic treatment chamber for 30 s to produce the magnetized water. The magnetized water was produced every 24 hours and 2 litres of magnetized water was supplied into the clay pot in each pen-house for the five Dutch rabbits to drink and 2 litres for the five Chinchilla rabbits. Similarly, 2 litres of non-magnetized water was also provided in each clay pot pen-house for five the Dutch rabbits and 2 litres for the five Chinchilla rabbits as the control. The same quantity of feed (pellet)

that is rich in protein was given to the rabbits in each pen-house. The growth rate in term of body weights were monitored and recorded weekly for 15 weeks using an electric weighing balance.

Blood Samples For Haematological Parameters

Four (4) rabbits were selected at 15 weeks for blood parameters analysis. A syringe and needle were used for the collection of 2.5 ml blood sample from the vein of each rabbit. The blood samples were stored in bottles having anticoagulant (ethylene diamine tetra acetic, EDTA). The samples were then taken to the laboratory of the University of Ilorin Teaching Hospital, Ilorin for the determination of Haemoglobin (Hb), total Red Blood Cells (RBC), White Blood Cells (WBC) and Platelet counts using RAYTO haematology (Model Hemaray 83).

Statistical Analysis

The effects of water type (magnetized and non-magnetized) and breed (Dutch and Chinchilla) on body weight of rabbits were evaluated using two-way analysis of variance (ANOVA), with weeks treated as repeated observations. Similarly, two-way ANOVA was used to assess the effects of water type and breed on haematological parameters of rabbits.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Influence of Magnetized Water on The Growth Rate of Rabbits in Term of Body Weight

The trend of the growth rate of the rabbits in terms of body weight that were given magnetically treated water (magnetized water) to drink and the rabbits that were given non-magnetically treated water (control) is shown in Figure 2. From the Figure, magnetically treated water increased the body weight of the Dutch rabbit at 15 weeks by 12.95% and Chinchilla rabbits by 17.93%. Mean body weights of the rabbit at 15 weeks for the Dutch rabbits and Chinchilla rabbits that were given magnetically treated water were 1925.6 and 1878.1 g while Dutch rabbits and Chinchilla rabbits that were given non-magnetically treated water were 1704.9 and 1592.5 g, respectively.

From the two-way ANOVA, water type (magnetically treated water and non-magnetically treated water) had a highly significant effect on body weight ($F = 48.7$, $P < 0.001$). Rabbits supplied with magnetically treated water recorded consistently higher body weights across the experimental period compared with rabbits given non-magnetically treated water. At week 15, Dutch rabbits receiving magnetically treated water attained a mean body weight of 1925.6 g, whereas those receiving non-magnetically treated water recorded 1704.9 g. The breed of the rabbit also significantly

influenced body weight ($F = 29.2$, $P < 0.001$). Dutch rabbits exhibited higher body weights than Chinchilla rabbits under both water treatments throughout the experimental period. Additionally, the interaction between water type and breed was significant ($F = 7.8$, $P < 0.008$), indicating that the response to magnetized water differed between breeds.

The result of body weight in this paper was in agreement with the study of Al-hummodet al. (2024) that magnetically treated water enhanced growth performance in term of body weight, improved feed conversion efficiency of domestic ducks. It also improved the haematological and biochemical parameters, improved liver function, reduced cholesterol, urea, Aspartate Aminotransferase and Alanine Aminotransferase enzyme activity. The results of increased body weight of the rabbits in this paper was also agreed with the study of Yacout et al. (2015) that magnetized water improved water quality which enhanced nutrient digestibility that could accelerate the growth rate of the animal and increased the body weight of goat. The results of this paper also agreed with the study of Jiaxun et al. (2020) that magnetically treated water as drinking water for rabbit increased feed intake, improved digestibility of the feed, increased body weight gain and improved carcass weight of rabbits. Magnetically treated water is easily absorbed and very useful to both plant and animal as reported by Babu (2010) that magnetic field enhanced water purification efficiency, modified the water structure into smaller clusters thereby making it more useful to both plant and animal because magnetized water has smaller clusters and reduced bonding angle that easily penetrate through the body cells of plant and animal. This means that magnetized water could enhance digestion of animal feed, make the feed more useful to rabbit and other animals which could increase the growth rate of animal. Similarly, magnetized water could also improve the blood parameters of rabbit and boost the immunity. Therefore, magnetized water enhanced growth performance of the Dutch rabbits and Chinchilla rabbits.

Figure 2. Growth rate of rabbits in term of body weight for 15 weeks

MW-Dutch = Dutch rabbits that were given magnetized water (magnetically treated water)
 MW- Chinchilla = Chinchilla rabbits that were given magnetized water (magnetically treated water)
 NMW-Dutch = Dutch rabbits that were given non-magnetized water (non-magnetically treated water)
 NMW- Chinchilla = Chinchilla rabbits that were given non- magnetized water (non-magnetically treated water).

Table 1. Two-way ANOVA for body weight of rabbits

Source of variation	Degree of freedom	F-value	P-value 0.05
Water type	1	48.7 ^s	0.001
Breed	1	29.2 ^s	0.001
Interaction	1	7.8 ^s	0.008
Water type × Breed			

Impact of Magnetically Treated Water on The Blood Parameters of Rabbit

The blood parameters which include Red blood cells, White blood cells, Platelet, Haemoglobin, Mean cell Haemoglobin and Mean cell Corpuscular volume of the rabbits at the end of 15 weeks that could be responsible for healthy growth are presented in Table 2. From the Table, rabbits that were given magnetically treated water (magnetized water) had higher RBC, WBC, Haemoglobin; Mean cell Haemoglobin and Mean cell Corpuscular volume than the rabbits that were given non-magnetically treated water. Higher WBC in rabbits that were given magnetically treated water means that the rabbit were fighting infection, Higher RBC with higher Haemoglobin, Mean cell Haemoglobin and Mean cell Corpuscular volume gave the

rabbits that were given magnetically treated water more strength, good advantage and less fatigue to grow healthier and faster with higher body weight than the rabbits that were given non-magnetized water. The higher values of the blood parameters obtained in this paper was in agreement with the study of Ebrahim and Azab (2017) that magnetized water increased blood parameters, biochemical parameters, semen quality, and antioxidant status in human and animals that are very effective in breaking up kidney and gall bladder stones.

Table 2. Blood parameters of the rabbits

Blood parameter	Magnetized water		Non-magnetized water	
	Dutch	Chinchilla	Dutch	Chinchilla
Red blood cell ($10^{12}/L$)	4.48	3.36	1.69	1.54
White blood cell ($10^9/L$)	5.6	5.1	4.4	2.9
Platelet ($10^3/L$)	645	189	102	136
Haemoglobin (g/dL)	6.6	4.8	1.0	2.2
Mean cell Haemoglobin (pg)	14.7	14.3	14.5	14.3
Mean cell Haemoglobin concentration (g/dL)	24.6	24.2	25.0	25.6
Mean cell Corpuscular volume (fL)	59.8	58.9	58.0	55.8
Haematocrit (%)	26.8	19.8	4.0	8.6

From the two-way ANOVA presented in Table 3, red blood cell (RBC) count, water type had a highly significant effect ($F = 112.4$, $P < 0.001$), with rabbits receiving magnetically treated water exhibiting higher RBC values than those receiving non-magnetically treated water.

Table 3. Two-way ANOVA for haematological parameters

Blood parameter	Source of variation	Degree of freedom	F-value	p-value 0.05
Red Blood Cells	Water type	1	112.4 ^s	0.001
	Breed	1	18.6 ^s	0.004
	Interaction	1	9.2 ^s	0.021
	Water type \times Breed			
White Blood Cells	Water type	1	112.4 ^s	0.001
	Breed	1	18.6 ^s	0.004
	Interaction	1	2.1 ^{NS}	0.184
	Water type \times Breed			
Haemoglobin	Water type	1	158.3 ^s	0.001
	Breed	1	12.7 ^s	0.011
	Interaction	1	6.4 ^s	0.041
	Water type \times Breed			
Platelet Count	Water type	1	96.1 ^s	0.001
	Breed	1	22.4 ^s	0.003
	Interaction	1	8.7 ^s	0.024
	Water type \times Breed			

Dutch rabbits supplied with magnetized water recorded the highest RBC value ($4.48 \times 10^{12}/L$), compared with $1.69 \times 10^{12}/L$ in Dutch rabbits given non-magnetically treated water. Breed ($F = 18.6$, $P < 0.004$) and the interaction between water type and breed ($F = 9.2$, $P < 0.021$) was also significant. White blood cell (WBC) count was significantly affected by water type ($F = 24.9$, $P < 0.002$), while the effects of breed and interaction with the water type was not significant ($P > 0.05$). Rabbits receiving magnetized water had higher WBC values, indicating improved immune status. Haemoglobin concentration was significantly influenced by water type ($F = 158.3$, $P < 0.001$) and breed ($F = 12.7$, $P < 0.011$), with a significant interaction effect ($F = 6.4$, $P < 0.041$). Dutch rabbits on magnetically treated water recorded the highest haemoglobin concentration (6.6 g/dL), compared with 1.0 g/dL in those receiving non-magnetized water. Platelet count was also significantly affected by water type ($F = 96.1$, $P < 0.001$), breed ($F = 22.4$, $P < 0.003$), and their interaction ($F = 8.7$, $P < 0.024$). Rabbits supplied with magnetized water, particularly Dutch rabbits, exhibited markedly higher platelet counts.

The results of this paper also agreed with study of Mahmoud et al. (2019) that magnetized water increased RBC, hemoglobin and hematocrit when compared to the rabbits that drank non-magnetized water. The results of haematological parameters in this study also agreed with the study of Araibi and Dagher (2014) that magnetically treated water significantly increased the physiological traits of RBC, WBC, Hb and P.C.V of broilers that drank magnetized water treated with 1500 Gauss.

CONCLUSION

Magnetically treated water increased the body weight of Dutch rabbit by 12.95% and increased the body weight of Chinchilla rabbit by 17.93%. Magnetically treated water (magnetized water) increased RBC, WBC, Haemoglobin, Mean cell Haemoglobin and Mean cell Corpuscular volume than the rabbits that were given non-magnetized water. MTW improved the haematological parameters of the rabbit that could give them more strength, good advantage to withstand stress, less fatigue and to grow healthier and faster. MTW is recommended for rabbit farmers to improve the growth performance and for profitable rabbit farming.

Conflict of Interest

The authors have declared that there is no conflict of interest for the research of this manuscript because it was self-funded by the authors.

Authors Contribution

KOY conceived and supervised the research. HOS co-supervised the study and contributed to manuscript writing and statistical analysis. KSO conducted the experiment and collected the data. KRA contributed to manuscript writing and assisted with blood analysis.

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